

Agai, Lapai, Kasha, Mokwa, and Pateggi were surveyed (523 fields). Ricefields were examined at 9 spots (the four corners, midway along each edge, and at the center).

During 1985-87 cropping seasons, BI occurred most frequently. It affected rice at all stages of development and was most severe on late-planted seedlings.

Other fungi diseases observed, in order of prevalence, were brown spot [caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan]; leaf scald [*Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi]; glume discoloration (many pathogens); sheath blight [*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn]; stem rot [*Sclerotium oryzae* Catt]; sheath rot

[*Sarocladium oryzae*]; bakanae [*Gibberella fujikuroi* (Sawada), Ito]; false smut [*Ustilagoidea virens* (Cke) Tak]; and narrow brown leaf spot [*Cercospora oryzae* Miyake].

Rice yellow mottle virus and unconfirmed bacterial blight symptoms were found occasionally. □

Insect management

Incidence of rice stem borer (SB) in the Punjab

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We surveyed incidence of rice SB *Scirpophaga* spp. and *Sesamia* spp. in the Punjab. Samples of rice stubble were collected at harvest from 98 locations in 1986 and from 60 locations in 1987 and dissected to determine tiller infestation and larvae/hill.

Overall tiller infestation was 25% in 1986 and 18% in 1987 (see figure). Traditional rice-growing Kalar tract and Ahmad Nagar were badly infested; Gujarat, Mandi Bahauddin, and Sheikhupura were comparatively less infested.

SBs found were yellow rice SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.), white SB

Incidence of rice SB in the Punjab, 1986-87.

S. innotata (Wlk.), and the pink graminaceous SBs *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and *S. uniformis* (Dudg.).

Scirpophaga spp. made up 357 of 362 larvae collected in 1986, and 1,291 of 1,296 larvae collected in 1987. □

Whitefly (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) - a potential pest of rice in West Africa

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Whiteflies are pests of many crops and also vectors of several plant virus diseases. Whiteflies on rice were first reported in 1966, when *Aleurocybotus indicus* D. and S. was identified in Satara, India. In 1970, *Bemisia tabaci*

M. and H. was found on rice in Madras, India.

A. indicus was reported to be restricted to India, with its preferred hosts graminaceous grasses *Chloris barbata* and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. But *A. indicus* was reported in Africa in April 1977, on irrigated rice at Richard Toll, Senegal. In recent years, it has spread to Mauritania, Senegal, Burkina Faso, Nigeria, and Niger.

The insect attacks rice plants from seedling to flowering stages. During the hot, dry season, especially in Feb, Mar,

and Apr, the insect is seen in irrigated rice at the IITA experimental farm at Ibadan. It has become a serious problem in screenhouses and insect rearing cages. When infestation is high, black sooty mold that develops on rice leaves can cause withering and plant death.

In the course of screening for *Diopsis longicornis* in the screenhouse, we found no *Oryza sativa* or *O. glaberrima* varieties that were tolerant of whitefly (500 entries tested).

A calcid larval parasite, *Encarsia* sp. found at Ibadan is definitely not

Encarsia formosa, a larval parasite of other whiteflies. Identification of the whitefly collected at Ibadan was verified by L. M. Russell, U.S. Department of Agriculture at Beltsville, Maryland, and D. J. Williams, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology (CIE). The parasite was identified by A. Polaozek of CIE. □

A method for rearing armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* Guenée (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on graminaceous hosts

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Armyworms often are reared in petri dishes with moistened paper towel and cut rice leaves to track development of individuals. But this method entails changing of plants and removing fecal material daily and is unreliable. Also larval survival is low because of high levels of fungal or bacterial infections.

We have designed a setup to minimize these disadvantages (see figure).

One-mo-old host plants are uprooted. Individual tillers are separated, wrapped

Improved method for rearing armyworm. IIRRI, 1988.

with moistened cotton, and placed in 10.5- × 2.5-cm test tubes. A cardboard plug prevents larvae from drowning.

Each test tube with plant is enclosed in a 19- × 4-cm cylindrical mylar cage with nylon mesh vents on the side and top. Nylon mesh attached to the base of the cylinder traps fecal material and aerates it to prevent fungal or bacterial infection.

One first-instar larva is placed on each host plant, using a moist camel hair brush. Caged plants with larvae are held upright in a wooden rack. (We use a compartmentalized 47- × 85-cm seedbox to accommodate 60 setups.) Plants are replaced every 3 d.

Average pupation of *S. m. acronyctoides* larvae was higher with this method than with using petri dishes (see table). □

Pupation of *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* reared on graminaceous host plants. IIRRI laboratory and greenhouse, Jun-Jul 1988.

Plant	Pupation ^a (%)	
	Petri dish method	Whole plant method
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	0	100 ± 0
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	20 ± 0.45	100 ± 0
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	40 ± 0.55	100 ± 0
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	20 ± 0.45	80 ± 0.45
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	40 ± 0.55	80 ± 0.45
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	40 ± 0.55	80 ± 0.45
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	20 ± 0.45	60 ± 0.55
\bar{X}	26 ± 0.15	86 ± 0.15

^a Av of 5 replications.

Simulated yellow stem borer (YSB) population dynamics: sensitivity and application

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We analyzed the sensitivity of a simulation model of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* population dynamics (SIMYSB) to changes in structure and parameter values.

For coarse sensitivity analysis, five mortality factors—egg predation; plant age; and parasitization of eggs, larvae, and pupae—were sequentially omitted from the model, to determine their significance for YSB larval population dynamics. Fine sensitivity analysis involved increasing and decreasing development, immigration, and oviposition rates by 20% to determine their relative importance in the system.

Without the effects of egg predation, egg parasitization, or plant age, larval population fluctuated at a relatively high level in both generations (Fig. 1). Without larval or pupal parasitization, the fluctuating level was relatively low, particularly in the first generation. On the whole, egg predators, egg parasites, and plant age are the most important factors regulating YSB populations.

1. Effect of omitting different mortality factors on simulated YSB larval populations in 1987 WS. 1 = with all effects (reference model), 2 = without egg predation, 3 = without egg parasitization, 4 = without effect of plant ages on larval survival, 5 = without larval parasitization, 6 = without pupal parasitization.

Response of larval populations to changes in egg, larval, and pupal development rates was highly proportional and asymmetrical (Fig. 1). This implies that rates are important variables, because they have large, complex effects on the system. Changes in immigration rate brought about an exactly proportional (20%) and symmetrical ($\pm 20\%$) effect on insect population across the season (Fig. 2b). Response to changes in oviposition rate was highly proportional but